

Southwood Multispecies Land Use Plan: Ecological Futures, Land Commons, and Everyday Stewardship

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Neighborhood Resilience through Adaptive Urban Ecologies

*"The land gives,
the land wants back." (1)*

Antônio Bispo dos Santos (1959–2023),
Brazilian Quilombola thinker and
agroecological philosopher

This plan envisions the neighborhood as a multispecies landscape. This means it is shared and shaped by human and more than human life. Rooted in this principle, it redefines infrastructure as a dynamic assemblage; in other words, a set of interdependent elements that evolve through adaptation, dynamic replacement, and reconnection instead of a fixed landscape governed only by humans.

Therefore, this plan treats urban infrastructures (e.g., ecological, social, or physical) as open, relational systems that evolve through continuous processes of repair, regeneration, and reassemblage, functioning through associative interactions between humans and more than humans. This approach is not new, but it builds on the concept of **assemblage** (2), emphasizing **co-evolution**, **adaptability**, and **interconnectedness** across periods of relative stability or episodic disturbance, shaping resilience at times of change and uncertainty.

Assemblage thinking as applied to urban systems, explores fluid, adaptive, and uneven relational dynamics between people, material objects, forms of governance, and designed environments. Colin McFarlane (3), for example, emphasizes that urban life is continuously shaped by distributed agency, sociomaterial interaction, power asymmetries, and collective imaginaries. Thus, assemblages are open systems, in which new configurations, alliances, and possibilities emerge through friction, adaptation, and chance.

In the broader context of Austin, a city facing pressures of real estate speculation, redevelopment, social displacement, ecological crisis, and climate stress, this framework is essential. Following the assemblage perspective, the context in which Southwood is inserted must not be seen simply as a set of infrastructures, but as a constantly evolving field of sociomaterial relations: built infrastructure, such as bike

lanes, stormwater systems, parks, shared spaces, tree canopies, mobility corridors, and private yards and should support living ecologies as a condition of resilience.

Emergence and potential are central to resilience. In Southwood, resilience must be cultivated through by enabling emergent relationships between green spaces and transit hubs, between residents and the shared stewardship of commons, between informal economies and public life. Such dynamics go beyond what static urban forms and top-down initiatives can deliver. Emergent relationships allow the neighborhood to reorganize, adapt, and innovate in response to ongoing disturbances such as socio-economic pressure, extreme heat, flooding, and energy disruption. Planning for resilience means making space for uncertainty, improvisation, and collective agency, and not prescribing outcomes in advance.

Distributed agency is also critical. Adaptive capacity is achieved beyond formal institutions and must be embedded in grassroots practice, for example, through community gardens, food networks, micro-energy systems, shared workshops, and everyday acts of stewardship. Through these open, participatory models of governance, urban transformation can be shaped by decentralized initiatives that allow resilience to emerge from diverse actors and spaces.

Finally, **commons and collective repair must be institutionalized as foundational practices.** Beyond green infrastructure, Southwood's resilience depends on cultivating urban **commons**: spaces and systems maintained through mutual care. Urban forestry, decentralized water systems, and community-run knowledge hubs form socio-ecological assemblages that heal the urban fabric by supporting and enhancing ecosystems.

This also requires a design ethic that values openness over rigid control. Richard Sennett argues that public spaces governed by rigid order suppress the creativity and adaptability essential to resilience. In *The Uses of Disorder* (4), he explores how open frameworks invite creative reuse, evolving alliances, and the organic growth of place. In Southwood, social and ecological infrastructures must be designed as open, adaptable systems, welcoming variation, emergent connections, and complex interactions. Resilience here means more than absorbing shock; it requires a city in motion: an assemblage capable of transformation and regeneration in the face of uncertainty.

(1) Santos, Antônio Bispo dos. *A terra dá, a terra quer*. São Paulo: Edições Ubu, 2021.

(2) Dubuffet J. As quoted in: Sendra P, Sennett R. *Designing Disorder: Experiments and Disruptions in the City*. London: Verso, 2020.

(3) McFarlane C. *Assemblage and critical urbanism*. *City*. 2011;15(2):204–224. doi:10.1080/13604813.2011.568715.

(4) Sennett R. *The Uses of Disorder: Personal Identity and City Life*. New York: W. W. Norton & Company, 1970.

Ben White Blv, Southwood, Spring 2016

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Author's garden in Southwood, Spring 2016

VISION: Statement

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“To cultivate a resilient neighborhood where ecological integrity, cultural identity, and social equity shape everyday life through shared spaces, land stewardship, and the regeneration of natural capital that supports both human and more-than-human well-beings.”

10310 S.H. 71 - Ben White Blvd. in Austin, T

10309 S.H. 71 - Ben White Blvd. in Austin,

PAST: 1950-2000's

Southwood: a new neighborhood

By the early 1960s, the farmlands south of the Colorado River were transforming into a new suburban frontier. The 1958 Austin Plan, developed by Pacific Planning and Research (page 8), envisioned South Austin primarily as a low-density residential zone, aligned with the postwar ideal of car-oriented suburban living. Green infrastructure was narrowly interpreted as flood control, limited to the creek corridors of Williamson and West Bouldin, with little consideration for broader ecological connectivity or open space networks. An industrial hub was designated near the emerging junction of Ben White Boulevard and I-35, a strategic location that remains active today and was planned to support regional logistics and employment.

The opening of Ben White Boulevard and the development of Southwood Mall in the mid-1960s exemplified this rapid suburban expansion. As families moved south in search of affordable homeownership, new infrastructure enabled the growth of self-contained residential and commercial districts. Southwood Mall, Austin's first enclosed, air-conditioned mall—emerged as a modern retail anchor, complete with a Sears, library branch, and movie theater. However, its prominence was short-lived. The arrival of Barton Creek Square Mall in the early 1980s drew shoppers with its larger scale and wider retail offerings. Later, the opening of Central Market in 1994 signaled a shift toward lifestyle-centered, walkable retail environments. These transitions reflect the broader evolution of South Austin's urban form, from postwar sprawl to more diversified and consumer-driven development patterns by the end of the 20th century.

Previous page: Ben White Blv and Clawson St, 1971 (top); Ben White Blv and Banister St, 1971 (bottom)
 (Source: UT Perry Castaneda Library Map Collection)

Austin, Census District Map, 1940 (Source: UT Perry Castaneda Library Map Collection)

Austin Aerial Imagery, 1940 (Source: <https://austin.maps.arcgis.com/home/index.html>)

As of 1970, the Southwood area (Census Tracts 20.02 and 20.03*) had a combined population of 3,878 residents, with a density of approximately 2,934 people per square mile. The neighborhood was 99.5% White, with 0.3% Black or African American, and 0.3% Other races. Most households (78.8%) were composed of husband-wife families, while 10.5% were other family types and 10.7% were individuals living alone, predominantly women. Among families, 65.5% had children under 18, reflecting a conventional suburban demographic.

Educationally, 62.8% of residents aged 25 and over had completed high school, and 17.4% had attended college, though only 3.8% had completed a 4-year college degree. Employment was high, with 65.9% of residents aged 16 and older participating in the labor force, of which 63.2% were employed, and only 0.9% were unemployed. These figures illustrate a predominantly white, working- to middle-class suburban community shaped by the postwar boom, with modest educational attainment and a strong labor market presence.

By 1990 and further into 2023, Southwood’s population aged significantly, with notable growth in residents over 55 and a relative decline in children and teens. While the 25–44 age group remained dominant, reflecting continued appeal to working adults, the area saw a steady shift away from the mid-century family structure, suggesting changing household dynamics, declining birth rates, and the early impacts of demographic transition and gentrification.

Population pyramid: 1970, 1990 Decennial Census and 2023 (5-y ACS) Population by Age data.

*U.S. Census Bureau. 1970 Decennial Census, Summary Tape File 1. Data for Census Tracts 20.02 and 20.03, Travis County, Texas. Accessed via Social Explorer, April 2025.

In 2014 the city adopted the South Austin Combined Neighborhood Plan as an extension of the Imagine Austin comprehensive vision. In this plan, the community expressed strong interest in preserving neighborhood character while expanding connectivity, bike infrastructure, and access to green space.

The plan laid out an extensive series of policies and actions, including implementation tools such as character districts that proposed zoning overlays targeting sidewalk completion, safer street crossings, public art, and neighborhood-serving mixed-use hubs along corridors like Stassney and Manchaca. Civic and commercial areas were reimagined through illustrative visions, aiming to knit together social, cultural, and ecological fabric.

Despite the proposed plan, implementation has been minimal over the past decade. Though zoning ordinances were adopted, many envisioned improvements—like protected bike lanes, stormwater infrastructure, and housing diversification—remain unbuilt or unfunded. Several proposed plan amendments since 2016 (e.g., to shift character districts toward mixed-use designations) indicate continued developer interest but mixed community support. Integration of higher density nodes with active transit also remains minimal.

Accelerated growth in the last decade have increased the necessity for balancing growth and affordability, retrofit infrastructure, and protect environmental assets like Williamson Creek amid climate stress. Finally, support to active mobility and collaborative stewardship initiatives in limited to non-existent.

The Austin Plan, by Pacific Planning Research, 1958

The Portal to Texas History, <https://texashistory.unt.edu/ark:/67531/metaph193708/m1/1/>

TODAY: Environment

The Southwood neighborhood lies adjacent to Williamson Creek but remains spatially and functionally disconnected from it. Despite the creek’s ecological value and cultural resonance, physical access is limited and poorly formalized. This lack of integration diminishes the neighborhood’s exposure to urban nature and restricts equitable access to one of South Austin’s most significant riparian systems. Residents have long voiced interest in trails, gathering spaces, and habitat restoration, but the area still lacks safe, public access to this natural corridor.

Another underutilized asset in Southwood is the abandoned Union Pacific rail line spur along South 1st St. As identified in the 2021 Vision Plan (1), this corridor could support low-impact trails, native vegetation restoration, and connections to nearby neighborhoods and transit routes. Yet it remains dormant. Without formal activation, this space contributes to the fragmentation of habitat and human mobility networks alike.

(1) City of Austin. Central Williamson Creek Greenway Vision Plan. Watershed Protection Department, 2021 (<https://www.austintexas.gov/department/central-williamson-creek-greenway>).

Produced after 2021 Austin Land Use Inventory (<https://data.austintexas.gov>)

In a broader context, Austin’s green infrastructure remains highly fragmented, with disconnected patches of parks, riparian zones, and habitat corridors. Southwood, centrally located near sensitive areas like the Barton Springs Greenbelt, is well positioned to strengthen ecological connectivity citywide.

While Southwood has schools and underutilized green spaces, and highly impervious commercial areas—up to 90% coverage—limit ecological performance. However, these conditions offer clear opportunities by improving pavement permeability, introducing rain gardens, green roofs, and decentralized water collection.

Existing green infrastructure, including parks, open space, preserved natural areas, riparian corridors, and undeveloped parcels.

Produced after 2021 Austin Land Use Inventory (<https://data.austintexas.gov>)

% of Canopy Change, 2010-2022. Produced after the City of Austin tree canopy coverage raster data (<https://data.austintexas.gov>) and 2020 Census Block.

Austin Region	Canopy Change	Residential Density	Key Insights*
Central	-25 to -10%	Increasing	Direct link between redevelopment and canopy loss
South	-15 to -5%	Increasing	Multifamily growth driving moderate canopy reduction
North & Far South	+5 to +20%	Stable to Slight Increase	Lower development pressure allows for canopy recovery
West	-5 to +5%	Low	Canopy largely preserved due to larger parcels and conservancy

* Source: <https://data.austintexas.gov>

The canopy change in Austin from 2010 to 2022 reveals stark spatial disparities, reflecting the ecological toll of unchecked redevelopment and habitat fragmentation. Canopy loss is most pronounced in South and East Austin—areas undergoing dense redevelopment and increasing residential density. Accelerated urbanization, compounded by protracted droughts and extreme weather events (notably the 2021 and 2023 winter storms), has heightened climate vulnerability in these zones. These patterns underscore the environmental costs of densification absent green infrastructure planning.

Source: 2021 Tree Canopy data (<https://data.austintexas.gov>)

Land Use Type	Land Area	Canopy Area	Canopy Density*	Canopy Share
Residential	72.3 %	37.5 %	51.7 %	70.8 %
Commercial	7.3 %	0.6 %	8.1 %	1.12 %
Other	20.4 %	12.3 %	(varies)	28.1 %

* as % of Land Area

Nearly 40% of Southwood’s tree canopy lies within residential areas, making it highly vulnerable to unchecked densification. As density increases, canopy loss threatens local resilience and worsens urban heat. Expanding tree cover along active mobility corridors and in impervious, non-residential zones is critical to mitigating heat island effects and supporting climate adaptation.

Source: 2021 Land Use Inventory data (<https://data.austintexas.gov>)

Land Use Type	Land Area	Impervious Area	Impervious Density*	Impervious Share
Residential	72.3 %	25.1 %	34.8 %	62.4 %
Commercial	7.3 %	6.5 %	90.1 %	16.2 %
Other	20.4 %	8.7 %	(varies)	21.35 %

* as % of Land Area

Although nearly 60% of the area remains non-impervious, runoff pollution remains a concern due to Williamson Creek crossing the area. Extended dry periods, punctuated by short, intense storm events, limit soil infiltration and increase flood risk—increasing the vulnerability of even relatively permeable landscapes under erratic rainfall and climate stress.

A significant portion of Southwood lies within the FEMA 100-year floodplain, exposing many parcels to recurrent flood risks, particularly as storm intensity increases with climate change. In response, the City of Austin has implemented voluntary buyouts of high-risk properties along Williamson Creek, particularly in areas such as Westgate and Heartwood, aiming to convert these parcels into restored green spaces and flood buffers.

The Williamson Creek Flood Risk Reduction Phase 1 study (2022) (1) evaluated multiple mitigation strategies. Among the preferred options are a combination of channel modifications, ecosystem restoration, and strategic buyouts to permanently remove vulnerable structures

While these efforts help reduce flood risk, they fall short in fully addressing social equity, long-term monitoring, and measurable ecological outcomes for transforming these areas into green corridors. Current plans also lack clear frameworks for community stewardship, ecological co-benefits, and updated zoning to restrict future development in vulnerable areas. Future phases should integrate these elements to ensure a more adaptive and equitable approach to flood mitigation—one that also enhances ecosystem provisioning.

(1) City of Austin. Williamson Creek Flood Risk Reduction Phase 1: Feasibility Study - Evaluation and Alternatives Analysis (COA 2015 PR2.1). Prepared by HDR Engineering, Inc., July 25, 2022. <https://www.austintexas.gov/sites/default/files/files/Watershed/flood/WMS-MiddleWilliamsonFeasibilityStudy.pdf>

0.2% and 1% Annual Chance Flood Hazard (FEMA) and parcels at flood risk. Parcels from the City of Austin Land Use Inventory, 2025 (<https://data.austintexas.gov>)

TODAY: Living Conditions & Development

The Southwood neighborhood is undergoing profound socioeconomic and environmental transformation. Data on rent burden reveal that over 21% of renter households spend more than half their income on housing, placing them in severely precarious conditions. Simultaneously, 12% of all households live below the federal poverty line—disproportionately among female-headed and nonfamily households—signaling deep economic strain. These are not isolated indicators but symptoms of broader, unchecked pressures exacerbated by a decade of rapid redevelopment across Austin. Spatial analysis of added building square footage reveals clusters of high-intensity construction precisely in areas already burdened by housing costs, compounding

the threat of displacement.

This accelerated redevelopment coincides with significant environmental losses. Neighborhood-scale analysis shows canopy decline in zones experiencing densification, reducing access to shade, storm-water absorption, and other ecological benefits at a time when extreme weather events are escalating. Together, these pressures risk fracturing the social and ecological fabric of the neighborhood.

A more resilient Southwood demands a planning framework that recognizes these interwoven dynamics. Redevelopment must go beyond expanding housing stock to actively address affordability, ecological function, and neighborhood stability.

Households (HH) below and above poverty status (ACS, 5-years 2018-2021, census tracts 20.02, 20.03; Source: Social Explorer)

Households (HH) under rent burden (>30% total income) (ACS, 5-years 2018-2021, census tracts 20.02, 20.03; Source: Social Explorer)

Previous Page: Contrasting housing forms in a rapidly redeveloping the Southwood neighborhood—an older single-story home beside a newly built two-story residence. (Photo by author, 2025)

Between 2010 and 2022, Austin experienced significant development, with new square footage heavily concentrated in central and south-central census blocks. Simultaneously, many of these same areas saw marked declines in tree canopy (see "Today: Environment"). Further analysis reveals a strong relationship between new construction and canopy loss, particularly in residential blocks with higher rent burden. These patterns suggest that redevelopment, while addressing housing demand, has brought uneven environmental costs.

From a policy standpoint, this underscores a critical imbalance: urban green infrastructure is too often treated as isolated environmental intervention rather than a spatial governance tool that mediates socio-ecological transformations. The canopy decline in densifying areas is not merely an ecological loss—it may signal displacement and the erosion of lived environmental functions, especially in historically affordable neighborhoods such as Southwood. This dynamic produces green infrastructural inequity: canopy is

lost where affordability wanes and preserved where privilege concentrates.

To ensure equitable and resilient growth, Austin must embed green infrastructure standards into land use and housing policy, prioritizing preservation and regeneration in vulnerable neighborhoods.

Total New Square Footage Added, 2010-2022.
 Produced after Issue Building Permit (<https://data.austintexas.gov>) and 2020 Census Block.

Planning must recognize these interconnected dynamics: redevelopment should not only address housing supply but also affordability, social stability, and environmental quality. Land use decisions must integrate green infrastructure, equitable investment, and protections for vulnerable populations. Without targeted intervention, rising development may deepen inequality and weaken the neighborhood's ecological and social fabric, thus its long-term resilience. Southwood's future resilience depends on a planning framework that connects people, place, and the living systems that sustain them.

Current Land Use Inventory: A Fragmented Landscape

The current land use inventory of the Southwood neighborhood reveals a highly residential-dominated pattern, with single-family homes covering approximately 65-70% of the total land area. Duplexes and three/fourplex units represent a minor share, lacking significant clustering. Apartment and condo developments are concentrated mostly along commercial edges, accounting for less than 10% of total area, which reflects a limited diversification of housing types. Commercial and office uses occupy fragmented strips primarily adjacent to major roads (Ben White Blv, South 1st st, and Slaughter St), contributing to a landscape of segregated activities rather than mixed-use integration. Manufacturing and warehousing sites are still present, especially along the northeastern edge, representing a legacy of industrial activity now increasingly disconnected from the neighborhood's residential core.

Parks and greenbelts, although present, are unevenly distributed and mainly concentrated along the Williamson Creek corridor, a highly fragmented habitat by surrounding development. Common areas and meeting and assembly spaces are minimal and not well-integrated within residential areas, pointing to a gap in public civic infrastructure.

FUTURE: Guiding Principles & Goals

Multispecies Neighborhood: Place-Making and Resilience

Unlike the rigid urban visions of the 1950s and 60s, today's cities no longer follow a single model focused on economic growth. Environmental crises, climate change, and social shifts have challenged traditional planning frameworks. Instead, cities are shaped by overlapping identities and evolving needs. Underused or rigid spaces—like parking lots, utility corridors, and engineered floodplains—can be reimagined as open, multispecies, multifunctional public spaces beyond exchange value where ecological systems and social life intersect. This approach positions public

space as active and biodiverse infrastructure, vital to daily life and urban resilience.

This multispecies vision for planning and design moves beyond static blueprints and overly regulated spaces. It embraces **open boundaries, layered ecologies, and dynamic social interactions**. Within these systems, people, species, and networks share and co-create adaptable environments. The aim is not only to withstand disruption—ecological, climatic, or social—but to thrive through diversity, flexibility, and connectivity.

Principle 1 Restore and sustain natural capital through green infrastructure supported by food production, native plantings, soil health, and community stewardship—strengthening biodiversity, urban sustainability, and ecological connectivity across the neighborhood.

Principle 2 Foster a inclusive social fabric by supporting cultural expression, intergenerational gathering, and equitable access to both resources and nature—while ensuring decision-making reflects the lived experiences of all residents and their relationship to place.

Principle 3 Prepare to climate extremes by improving tree canopy, enhancing nature-based water and resources management, designing climate-adapted, walkable, and low-carbon build environments, and connecting local, accessible food-systems to the population.

MULTISPECIES LAND USE PLAN

User Guide

This diagram (next page) show a step-by-step guide to understanding the structure of the Southwood Multispecies Land Use Plan. The process begins with the **Current Land Use Inventory** (pages 28-29) and the definition of **Guiding Principles** (page 31), which shape the vision and values of the plan. From there, **Land Use Typologies** (Table 1, page 29) are developed as a foundational classification system. These typologies are then further analyzed through two lenses: the **Infrastructure & Functions Inventory** (Table 2, pages 34-35), which focuses on built systems

and their potential to support eco-productive urban strategies; and the **Natural-Cultural System** (Table 3, page 36), which highlights existing ecological and cultural layers. Each analysis phase leads to a focused set of goals—activating adaptive infrastructure and strengthening biocultural stewardship. Finally, the **Multispecies Land Use** (page 40-41) is a synthesized vision integrating mapping, typology, strategy, and ethics into a cohesive framework for regenerative urban transformation.

Table 1 Land Use Typologies This table defines the primary land use categories guiding the Multispecies Land Use Plan. Each typology is based on spatial characteristics, intensity of use, and ecological potential, forming the structural base for all subsequent functional and policy analyses.

Table 2 Shared Functions & Infrastructure This table maps each land use category to its associated functions (e.g., food production, public gathering) and infrastructures (e.g., stormwater systems, rooftop gardens), emphasizing the multifunctionality of urban systems across public and private realms.

Table 3 Natural-Cultural System Intersections This table explores how ecological features—such as flood zones, soil conditions, and canopy cover—intersect with land use categories and inform opportunities for stewardship, restoration, and climate adaptation.

Existing Land Use Inventory: Current Typologies and Challenges

The Southwood neighborhood’s existing land use inventory were clustered into broader categories to reflect their ecological and functional roles, highlighting both opportunities and challenges (see **Table 1**).

The core of the neighborhood remains dominated by single-family residential development, a legacy of 1960s suburbanization, while multifamily housing is fragmented and often adjacent to commercial and former industrial nodes—areas historically burdened by environmental impacts.

Notably absent are mixed-use residential environments that would support greater walkability, service access, and social diversity. Ecological connectivity is also limited, with critical habitat corridors along Williamson Creek fragmented by development.

This typology framework establishes a baseline for proposing restorative and adaptive strategies—prioritizing resilience, water management, integrated public spaces, and community-based stewardship

Category	Existing Land Uses	Primary Focus
Ecological & Open Space	Parks/Greenbelts, Preserves, Common Areas, Cemeteries, Undeveloped	Resilience, cooling, storm-water, habitat, recreation, food
Neighborhood Residential	Single Family, Mobile Homes, Duplexes, Three/Fourplex	Stabilize low/moderate density housing, enable gentle infill, water resilience & restore canopy
Resilient Multi-family Housing	Apartment/Condo, Retirement Housing, Semi-institutional Housing	Increase housing diversity, access, density near Community/mobility nodes - enhanced water management
Civic & Social Nodes	Educational, Government Services, Hospitals, Meeting & Assembly	Anchor public and social functions, support social capital - integrated ecological spaces
Mixed Use / Community Nodes	Mixed Use, Commercial, Office, Group Quarters	Enable walkable, service-rich centers with shared amenities - enhanced water management
Commercial & Repair-Oriented Nodes	Manufacturing, Warehousing, Misc. Industrial, Utilities	Support local economic resilience, green industry, maker spaces, integrated food systems
Mobility Nodes	Streets and Roads, Parking, Transportation Facilities, Rail	Ensure multimodal access, integrate transit, prioritize walkability through greenways

Table 1 Land use categories aligned with resilience and stewardship goals, identifying primary ecological and social focus areas for future planning.

(Previous page) **Map of existing land use distribution**, clustered into six typologies to highlight residential dominance, ecological areas, and commercial/industrial zones. Based on the City of Austin Land Use Inventory, 2025 (<https://data.austintexas.gov>).

Multispecies Neighborhood: Mapping Private and Public Spaces

FUNCTIONS			
Office	Workshop/Studio	Community kitchen	City hall
	Co-working space	School	Museum
Daycare			
Corner shop	Community kitchen		Cultural center
INFRASTRUCTURE			
Private rain harvesting	Stormwater system	Bike/pedestrian infrastructure	
	Shared garbage	Local street	Green belt trail
Backyard	Rooftop (green)	Transit corridor	
Driveway	Frontyard	Alley	Floodplain
PUBLIC SPACES			
	Shared rooftop (green)	Playground	Transit hub
Courtyard		Neighborhood plaza	Park
Private patio	Community garden	Grocery store	
	Public seating	Sports facility	Green belt/ Urban forest

SHARED BY FEW SHARED BY MANY

Cities are composed of elements that range in their degree of shared use, shaping how we experience urban life. Yet their multifunctional potential is often underutilized in planning. We propose that shared spaces offering rich ecological services should be prioritized in terms of accessibility, connectivity and community-based stewardship, while the social and environmen-

tal value of private spaces be enhanced through planning tools and design strategies that promote sustainability, social interaction and everyday usability.

(Above) Functional, Infrastructural, & Public elements of urban life.

(Next Page) Correlation matrix between urban elements and Land Use.

Trail by Williamson Creek, Southwood, Fall 2021

● ● ● ● ● directly shared feature/ function ——— indirectly shared/supportive function

Green Infrastructure

Civic & Social Infrastructure

Mobility & Access

Productive & Mixed-use

Land Use Category	Planning Goal	Shared Functions	Shared Infrastructure	Shared Public Spaces	Enabling Strategies
Ecological & Open Space	Restore ecological systems through connected green infrastructure and community stewardship (Principle 1)	Cultural center, Museum	Green belt trail, Stormwater system	Natural Reserve, Park, Urban forest	Public access easements through private parcels; Ecological zoning overlays; Community-led co-management
Neighborhood Residential	Support resilient, inclusive living with ecological infill and shared open space (Principle 2)	Daycare, Community kitchen	Alley, Shared garbage, Bike infrastructure, Stormwater system	Courtyard, Community garden, Urban forest	Green ADU Overlay Zones; Shared space grants for green retrofits; Resilient Home Toolkit for residents
Resilient Multi-family Housing	Expand housing diversity with climate-adaptive infrastructure and shared resources (Principle 3)	Co-working space, Workshop/Studio	Rooftop (green), Stormwater system, Floodplain Infrastructure, Driveways	Shared rooftop, Neighborhood plaza, Community garden, Urban forest	Shared facility mandates; Integrated Green-Blue Infrastructure Standards; Climate Co-op Zoning Bonuses
Civic & Social Nodes	Anchor public life and belonging through integrated civic and ecological spaces (Principle 2)	School, City hall, Cultural center	Rooftop (green), Stormwater system, Floodplain infrastructure, Transit corridor	Transit hub, Sports facility, Community garden, Urban forest	Civic-green infrastructure co-location incentives; Public Lands Stewardship Fellowship programs; Retrofit funds for nature-based solutions
Mixed Use & Community Nodes	Create walkable, climate-ready high-density hubs with shared services and mobility (Principle 3)	Corner shop, Office, Community kitchen	Rooftop (green), Local streets, Bike/pedestrian network	Shared rooftop, Public seating, Grocery store, Community garden, Urban forest	Green Alley Incentive Program; Plazas-as-Agroecology Labs; Community Node Activation Grants
Commercial & Repair-Oriented Nodes	Promote circular economies and urban productivity through sustainable infrastructure (Principle 1 + Principle 3)	Workshop, Maker spaces	Rooftop (green), Stormwater systems, Floodplain Infrastructure, Driveways, Loading docks, Utilities	Shared rooftop, Public seating, Community garden	Eco-industrial zoning overlays; Urban Forestry Fund expansion to include bioremediation; Green Industry Apprenticeships
Mobility Nodes	Ensure equitable, low-carbon access through green and multimodal corridors (Principle 3)	None specifically, but supports all above	Green belt trail, Transit corridor, Local streets	Transit hub, Shared bike/ped paths	Greenways + Streets integration; Participatory Design; Resilient Mobility Hubs

Table 2 Infrastructure and Function Inventory From private patios to greenbelts, this table maps a continuum of shared spaces that support ecological, social, and functional needs. Functions like community kitchens and co-working spaces are paired with green infrastructure, such as stormwater systems and rooftop gardens, while higher density

housing and community nodes are connected to urban forestes and community gardens, aiming for a multi-functional green infrastructure network. These connections support transformative approach to green space management, emphasizing ecological richness, resident engagement, and low-maintenance design.

Multispecies Neighborhood: Mapping Natural-Cultural System

Building on the mapped distribution of **functions, infrastructures, and public spaces** (pages 30-33) Southwood’s neighborhood plan reframes these elements as parts of a broader cultural landscape system. Instead of treating functional and public spaces as isolated components, they are understood as dynamic elements of an urban ecology, interconnected with natural systems. To promote transformative landscape dynamics, the plan prioritizes enhancing intersections between cultural and natural systems, weaving ecological and social infrastructures. Inspired by Schweiger (2012), the design process identifies and layers natural systems, void spaces, cultural systems, boundaries, and intersections to support a living, resilient urban ecology (1):

Systems/Spaces	Function/elements	Land Use Categories / Functions / Infrastructure / Public Space
Natural Landscape Systems	Network Cores: stable habitat cores that support above & below-ground biodiversity and hydrology	Ecological & Open Space (parks, greenbelt trails, floodplains, urban forest)
Spaces for Ecological Regeneration	Network Cores and Buffers: stabilize critical ecological zones by limit built footprints	Undeveloped lands, Ecological & Open Space (parks, greenbelt trails, floodplains, urban forest); Residential parcels along riparian zones and preserves
Natural-Cultural Intersections	Connecting Elements + Dynamic Matrix: points of socio-ecological hybridization and transformation	Community gardens adjacent to transit hubs, composting facilities, food forests, tiny urban forests, playgrounds in flood-adapted parks
Natural-Cultural Boundaries	Connecting Elements: edges where ecology and society interact	Interface between parks/urban forests and civic spaces; street edges with rain gardens, community plazas; private wildlife yards, tiny forests, trail corridors through neighborhoods
Cultural Landscape Systems	Surrounding Landscape Matrix: socially productive spaces and engineered infrastructure	Designed for everyday ecological stewardship and social exchange: Community gardens, plazas, shared rooftops, public seating areas, yards, schools, parks, mobility infrastructure

(1) Schweiger M. Ecological network planning: Exemplary habitat connectivity projects in Germany. Bonn: German Federal Agency for Nature Conservation (BfN); 2012.

Existing Natural-Cultural Systems, Intersections and Boundaries *Current conditions show fragmented ecological network cores, sharp divides between built and natural spaces, minimal ecological-cultural intersections, and weak ecological buffers along urban green spaces. Produced based on the City of Austin Land Use Inventory, 2025 (<https://data.austintexas.gov>).*

Strengthening these intersections restores soils, reactivates hydrological flows, and establishes ecological buffers, step-stones, and corridors. Through this integrated lens, urban planning becomes a regenerative act—connecting soils, waters, species, and communities into an evolving, resilient system. Although the natural-cultural systems maps presented are not formal land use designations, they offer a framework to guide future legislation, zoning overlays, and stewardship initiatives that advance Southwood’s vision of dynamic and adaptive urban ecologies.

Table 3 (previous page) *Land use categories aligned with resilience and stewardship goals, identifying primary ecological and social focus areas for future planning.*

Western Creek Bend This segment extends the floodplain corridor into adjacent residential fabric, enabling stormwater retention and habitat continuity while redefining underutilized space as part of Southwood’s ecological backbone.

Railroad Crossing At this road-ecology interface, expanded riparian buffers and pedestrian crossings reconnect fragmented systems - this section can be transformed in Blackland prairies transitioning to a native food forest along the riparian buffer zone.

Abandoned Railroad Spur Located along an abandoned railroad spur, this corridor links the neighborhood to the South 1st st and hosts spontaneous native plants, offering an ideal site for an active mobility trail and community garden, linking ecology, mobility, and stewardship.

South Congress Ave Crossing Currently isolated by multifamily housing and commercial lots, this confluence zone can be reimagined as a connective greenway—restoring creek access, fostering mobility, and embedding cultural and ecological functions into daily life.

South 1st st Crossing This transition zone blurs suburban parcels and natural systems through bioswale retrofits, tree canopy repair, and stewardship programs, offering residents both flood protection and active ecological participation.

Proposed Natural-Cultural Systems, Intersections and Boundaries *Proposed expansion of Southwood’s natural-cultural systems, intersections, and boundaries. Network cores (parks, floodplains, urban forests) are expanded to strengthen ecological connectivity, while surrounding residential and commercial areas are reframed as dynamic ecological-cultural boundaries. These transition zones are envisioned to hybridize urban and natural systems through stricter environmental standards, nature-based infrastructure, and shared spaces rooted in soil health, biodiversity, and community stewardship. Produced based on the City of Austin Land Use Inventory, 2025 (<https://data.austintexas.gov>).*

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Multispecies Neighborhood: Final Land Use Map

FEMA 100 years flood zone

- Ecological & Open Space
- Neighborhood Residential
- High-density, Resilient Housing
- Mixed-Use / Community Nodes
- Civic & Social Nodes
- Commercial, Productive & Repair-oriented Spaces
- Mobility & Transit Nodes

Produced based on the City of Austin Land Use Inventory, 2025
(<https://data.austintexas.gov>).

This **Multispecies Land Use Map** reflects a comprehensive process integrating ecological, infrastructural, and community priorities for Southwood. Beginning with a land use inventory and guiding principles, the plan developed typologies aligned with climate resilience, equity, and stewardship. Through mapping shared functions, infrastructure, and public spaces, each zone was evaluated for its ecological value and social potential. The final map weaves together high-density housing, green infrastructure, floodplain restoration, and community hubs, creating a polycentric and adaptive neighborhood. Everyday urban elements—like alleys, rooftops, and vacant lots—are reframed as essential spaces for biodiversity and climate action. This map envisions a regenerative urban fabric where human and non-human life can thrive through integrated, multispecies land use.

POLICY FRAMEWORK

Railroad cross over Williamson Creek, by Lansing Drive, Spring 2025

Ecological & Open Space

Goal Restore ecological systems and build **Natural Capital** through connected green infrastructure and community stewardship.

Objective By 2030, increase tree canopy by 20%, add 3+ new micro-parks, 2+ miles of greenways, restore 10+ acres of degraded soil zones, and expand the green infrastructure through compost and rain water harvesting systems.

Policy 1.1 Floodplain Restoration & Stewardship Zones: Rezone 5+ flood-prone and/or vacant parcels for ecological use, prioritizing areas along Williamson Creek. Implement co-stewardship agreements with local nonprofits or resident groups and establish **soil health** targets (e.g., organic matter %, compaction) for restoration projects.

Policy 1.2 Green Infrastructure Resilience Fund: Expand the Urban Forest Replenishment Fund into a Green Infrastructure Resilience Fund, using development impact fees to support tree planting, soil rehabilitation, local compost systems, and rain water harvesting systems. Tie contributions to any additional impervious cover thresholds (capped at 70%) to promote infiltration.

Policy 1.3 Community Soil & Forestry Knowledge Network: Establish a hybrid network (in-person + digital) for native plant propagation, soil restoration/monitoring, land care co-learning, and rain water harvesting systems. Support public access and stewardship/management of green infrastructure, and integrate workshops into public green space programming.

Policy 1.4 "Void Space" Preservation Ordinance: Rezone all floodplain-adjacent parcels and critical hydrological corridors with a maximum 30% impervious cover limit, requiring ecological restoration plans.

Soil health Soil health is the living foundation of neighborhood resilience. By restoring and protecting soil systems, we support biodiversity, water retention, carbon storage, and food potential—while anchoring cultural and ecological connections to land: this is building **Natural Capital**. This plan calls for adopting soil health indicators, guiding development away from disrupting underground networks and habitats, and promoting regenerative practices that heal urban landscapes from the ground up.

Urban forestry Recent climate extremes have decimated Austin's tree canopy, highlighting the urgent need for its regeneration. Urban trees are often treated as industrial waste and repurposed as mulch, rather than valued as ecological resources. Community-based events can promote tree observation, cultivation, and sapling stewardship, fostering urban forestry from the ground up. Caretaking—through planting, sowing, logging, and craft—builds social capital and shared knowledge, offering residents a way to engage while enhancing biodiversity.

Undeveloped Land, formerly farmland, by Manchaca and Ben White Blv, Spring 2024

Decentralized water systems In Southwood's vision for resilience, decentralized water systems supported by rainwater harvesting tanks are integral components of the green infrastructure. The existing conditions—degraded soils, high impervious surface areas, and rapid runoff—intensifies pollutant loads into creeks and increases dependence on centralized water supply systems with heavy ecological and carbon footprints. To counter this, the neighborhood must transition toward localized water retention, treatment, and infiltration strategies.

Soil restoration efforts, including the introduction of deep-rooted native perennials and rain gardens, can dramatically improve infiltration capacity, reduce surface runoff, and act as natural biofilters, cleansing rainwater before it reaches downstream ecosystems. Shared and private harvesting systems—integrated at block scale—can capture stormwater for multiple beneficial uses. Harvested rainwater can feed into gardens to enhance on-site infiltration, thereby supporting soil biodiversity, aquifer recharge, and the overall urban water cycle. Alternatively, surplus harvested rainwater can be locally treated to supplement non-potable or even potable water supply, reducing reliance on external infrastructure during droughts or service disruptions.

By embedding rainwater management into the very fabric of the neighborhood, the area can create a distributed, regenerative hydrological system. This system would not only enhance climate resilience but also foster new forms of collective stewardship, where neighbors co-manage infrastructure and green assets. Designing at the scale of blocks and microbasins—rather than isolated lots—ensures that the benefits of infiltration, cooling, habitat support, and storm mitigation are amplified, transforming rainwater from a liability into a shared, life-sustaining resource.

Upland Zone (Non-flooded – Urban Interface) This zone supports essential infrastructure—roads, homes, utilities—set back from the floodplain. Transition strategies include tree canopy restoration and permeable surfaces to reduce runoff and enhance the buffer between urban form and ecology.

Transitional Floodplain (0.2–1% Flood/Riparian Zone) This rewilded corridor includes flood-adapted food forests with species like elderberry (*Sambucus canadensis*), pawpaw (*Asimina triloba*), and spicebush (*Lindera benzoin*), offering seasonal harvest, habitat, and hydrological resilience through native restoration.

Creek Crossing & Trail Interface A nature trail with stepping stones and varied-width crossings invites visitors while preserving creek dynamics. Designed to manage flow and protect sensitive zones, it reconnects people with the restored waterway's evolving form.

Wet Prairie Edge (Non-forested 0.2–1% Flood/Riparian Zone) An open, floodplain prairie ecosystem supports herbaceous species requiring sunlight and seasonal saturation. This rare edge zone enhances biodiversity, filters runoff, and requires careful management due to its ecological sensitivity and unique species.

Williamson Creek by Meadow Creek Circle, Southwood, Spring 2025

Williamson Creek floodplain Southwood presents a unique opportunity to shift from reactive flood management toward a regenerative urban watershed approach. With many parcels already acquired through voluntary buyouts, the area can be reimagined as a dynamic floodplain landscape that tolerates and adapts to periodic inundation. Instead of relying solely on engineered defenses, Southwood should integrate floodplain reprofiling, expanded green infrastructure, and restored creekside ecologies. Strategies such as multi-use riparian parks, and adaptive urban edges allow the creek to evolve naturally within defined limits, reducing flood risks while providing social and ecological benefits. This aligns with the city's goals for climate resilience, equity, and ecosystem services. What remains missing is a robust implementation framework for stewardship, inclusive design, and long-term monitoring to ensure that restored lands function not just as buffers, but as thriving public landscapes in a changing climate.

Neighborhood Residential

Goal Support resilient, inclusive living with ecological infill and shared open space.

Objective By 2035, retrofit 50% of residential lots with climate-ready ADUs and/or ecological features—such as rain gardens and rainwater harvesting systems—and ensure that 90% of existing homes remain affordable at no more than 30% of household income.

Policy 2.1 **ADU Resilience Incentive Portal:** Create a one-stop grant platform combining Austin Energy and Austin Water rebates with local programs for tree planting, bioswales, and permeable paving. Prioritize outreach to low- and moderate-income households.

Policy 2.2 **Green ADU Overlay Zone:** Designate overlay zones where ADUs must meet permeability and green infrastructure thresholds, with additional incentives for integrating food gardens, rainwater systems, and native plantings.

Policy 2.3 **Soil Steward Mentorship Program:** Launch a city-backed **knowledge network**-mentorship and co-learning initiative-connecting homeowners with master gardeners, compost practitioners, and urban farmers to restore yard ecology and soil vitality.

Policy 2.4 **Residential Edge Greening Program:** Create a microgrant program and fast permitting track for homeowners who plant rain gardens, install native tree clusters, or restore soil in front yards bordering parks and greenbelts.

Knowledge Networks A Southwood Knowledge Exchange Program would advance ecological resilience, food security, and social cohesion by connecting farmers, city officials, researchers, and residents (1). It would offer training in native gardening, soil restoration, composting, small-scale food production, and community-based science through informal learning labs and demonstration sites embedded in public spaces. Cooperative workshops, gardens, and shared kitchens would serve as hubs for technical exchange and long-term stewardship building. Personal contact would anchor the network, while digital platforms—modeled on São Paulo's *Sampa+Rural* (2)—would broaden access across ages and tech-literacy levels. The city could seed this initiative through a Green Stewardship Fund sourced from development impact fees. By blending technical skill-building with community identity, the program would institutionalize shared ecological responsibility and support a resilient, regenerative future for Southwood.

(1) Malusà E, Schmidt C, Sławiński C, Brunori G. Knowledge networks for sustainable organic farming: A review. *Sustainability*. 2022;14(5):2960. doi:10.3390/su14052960

(2) Prefeitura de São Paulo. *Sampa+Rural* [Internet]. São Paulo: Secretaria Municipal de Desenvolvimento Econômico e Trabalho; [cited 2025 Apr 21]. Available from: <https://sampamaisrural.prefeitura.sp.gov.br>

Resilient Multi-family Housing

Goal Expand housing diversity with climate-adaptive infrastructure and shared resources

Objective By 2040, 60% of new projects must include shared amenities and achieve Green Building 3-star minimum.

Policy 3.1 Green Retrofit + Rooftop Mandate: Provide retrofit grants for green infrastructure and mandate rooftop gardens and on-site stormwater retention for buildings over 6 units.

Policy 3.2 Resident Training for Green Co-Stewardship: Partner with TreeFolks and Urban Forestry to train tenants in co-managing green infrastructure, composting systems, and shared outdoor spaces.

Policy 3.3 Cooperative Incentive Zoning: Offer density and height bonuses to climate-ready developments that include resident-managed cooperatives: shared kitchens, childcare, repair studios, and gardens. Require at least 10% of ground-level or 50% rooftop space be designated for collective use.

Policy 3.4 Tiny Urban Forest Infill Incentive: Require multifamily projects >10 units adjacent to floodplains, greenways, or parks to dedicate 10% of site area to a tiny urban forest planting.

Climate-ready design To ensure climate adaptation in Southwood's high-density multifamily buildings, new development should integrate climate-responsive design principles that minimize indoor overheating during extreme heat. Key strategies include installing external solar protections (such as shutters, blinds, or overhangs) to block direct sunlight before it enters living spaces, using thermal mass materials (like exposed concrete or brick) to absorb and slowly release coolness, and enabling natural cross-ventilation, especially through dual-aspect or traversing units. These passive measures—rooted in traditional architectural logic—reduce dependency on air conditioning, enhance summer comfort, and increase long-term resilience amid rising heat events.

Civic & Social Nodes

Goal Anchor public life and belonging through integrated civic and ecological spaces

Objective By 2035, ensure 100% of residents are within a 10-minute walk of a civic/communal/shared facility featuring at least two ecological resilience features.

Policy 4.1 Green Retrofit: Retrofit 100% of existing civic buildings with ecological infrastructure, including bioswales, soil decompaction, permeable paving, and native canopy and understory planting, following defined ecological performance standards.

Policy 4.2 Education Hubs: Co-locate Green Infrastructure Education Hubs within all public schools and libraries, offering soil stewardship programs, garden labs, and stormwater literacy workshops, and native plants/tree give-aways.

Policy 4.3 Fellowship: Launch a Public Lands Stewardship Fellowship, training volunteers in soil care, urban agriculture, biodiversity restoration, and the environmental history of Central Texas's landscapes.

Policy 4.4 Eco-Edge Activation Program: Mandate that all civic retrofits (schools, libraries, community centers) adjacent to parks or floodplains must include a publicly accessible edge treatment with rain gardens, habitat plantings, tiny forests, or stormwater trails.

Social capital The transformation of the former Southwood Mall area into a high-density, mixed-use hub reflects a shift from isolated land use zones to an integrated, relational urban fabric. Rather than designing housing, commerce, public space, and green areas as separate components, the focus is on the connections and synergies between them—supporting informal, meaningful social interactions.

Ground-level small businesses, shared kitchens, and food trucks are envisioned to activate the space daily, while open, tree-shaded plazas with embedded stormwater infrastructure with native planting for wildlife provide adaptable, climate-resilient gathering spaces. These flexible commons are not assigned fixed functions, but designed with the capacity for variation—hosting anything from farmers' markets and seasonal festivals to casual everyday use.

Three core elements define this new urban condition:

- (1) **direct connectivity** to surrounding neighborhoods, greenways, and transit nodes (like the Westgate Transit Center) via tree-shaded, protected active mobility corridors;
- (2) a **rhythm** of seasonal, weekly and daily programming through local food, community gardening, plant exchanges, and celebrations;
- (3) the presence of visible, **participatory social infrastructure**—community gardens, manual skill workshops, urban forestry, and gathering nodes—where residents can share and build skills that strengthen social cohesion, resilience, and care for place.

Mixed use & Community Nodes

Goal Create walkable, climate-ready high-density hubs with shared services and mobility.

Objective By 2035, establish 4 Community Nodes with plazas, markets, agroecological features, and connected bike infrastructure.

Policy 5.1 Nature-based solutions: Allow up to 5 stories in Community Nodes only for projects that integrate greenway connections with Mobility Nodes, bioswales, on-site stormwater retention, rainwater harvesting, and soil permeability or restoration zones (with measurable outcomes) into their site design.

Policy 5.2 Agroecological Hub Mandate: Require all new transit hubs or community nodes to integrate tiny forests, food forests, community gardens, and/or rain gardens.

Policy 5.3 Composting: Require all new commercial kitchens to implement organic waste separation systems and publicly report data through a Local Soil Network Exchange Platform to track waste diversion and compost production.

Policy 5.4 Connected Habitat and Soil Network Ordinance: New nodes must physically link green and soil systems block-to-block, not just have isolated gardens by integrating 15% of public realm surfaces as living ecological infrastructure (tree canopy, rain gardens, and permeable soils) to form continuous habitat and cooling corridors.

Native planting Native shrubs bring essential ecological value to mixed-use residential areas, supporting both human and wildlife needs. Species like Texas persimmon (*Diospyros texana*), yaupon (*Ilex decidua*), and agarita (*Mahonia trifoliolata*) are adapted to Central Texas's heat, drought, and poor soils, making them ideal for low-maintenance, high-performance plantings. These shrubs provide seasonal food and habitat for birds, pollinators, and small mammals, while also stabilizing soils and enhancing water infiltration. Some, like Anacacho (*Bauhinia lunarioides*), enrich soils through nitrogen fixation. Integrated into plazas, rooftops, and courtyards, native shrubs offer not just beauty, but critical ecosystem services—cooling microclimates, extending habitat corridors, and reinforcing the role of green infrastructure in dense urban settings.

Commercial & Repair-oriented Nodes

Goal Promote circular economies and urban productivity through sustainable infrastructure

Objective By 2040, repurpose at least 50% of underutilized commercial/light industrial parcels into green, productive hubs.

Policy 6.1 Food Forests, Urban Forestry & Bioremediation: Use the Soil & Forestry Fund to support ground-level or rooftop food forests, vertical farms, and edible landscapes, prioritizing sites with high impervious cover. Where soils are contaminated, require tiny forests and urban forestry management for bioremediation.

Policy 6.2 Resident Training for Green Co-Stewardship: Partner with TreeFolks and Urban Forestry to train tenants in co-managing green infrastructure, composting systems, and shared outdoor spaces.

Policy 6.3 Cooperative Incentive Zoning: Offer density and height bonuses to developments that include resident-managed cooperatives: shared kitchens, childcare, repair studios, and gardens. Require at least 10% of ground-level or rooftop space be designated for collective use.

Policy 6.4 Industrial Soil Infiltration Bonus: Offer tax reductions to local, light industrial/commercial property owners who convert $\geq 20\%$ of their impervious surface into permeable soils, including soil restoration and native landscaping zones.

Tiny Urban Forests Based on the Miyawaki method (1), tiny urban forests are powerful tools for ecological restoration and climate resilience. By densely planting native species in degraded urban soils, they rapidly create multilayered forests that mimic natural ecosystems, acting as stepping-stones for wildlife. Urban forests bioremediate contaminated soils by improving infiltration and soil health, while sequestering carbon at much higher rates than conventional urban greenery. Their small footprint makes them ideal for areas like commercial hubs, where cooling the urban microclimate are critical to adapting to climate and social challenges.

(1) Miyawaki A. Restoration of living environment based on vegetation ecology: theory and practice. *Ecol Res.* 2004;19(1):83-90. doi:10.1111/j.1440-1703.2003.00522.x.

Mobility Nodes

Goal Ensure equitable, low-carbon access through green and multimodal corridors.

Objective By 2030, build 4+ miles of separated bike lanes and greenways linking Williamson Creek to South 1st and Westgate areas, and to Westgate and South Congress Transit Centers.

Policy 7.1 Greenways: Implement Complete Streets Standards that require bioswales, permeable paving, and 60% tree canopy coverage on all new or retrofitted active mobility corridors.

Policy 7.2 Multimodal Paths: Expand the Urban Forest and Soil Health Fund to finance green corridor plantings that improve runoff infiltration and provide shade along multimodal paths.

Policy 7.3 Participatory Design: Launch Community Mobility Labs where residents co-design green streetscapes, monitor biodiversity, and steward roadside soils through **participatory mapping, design, governance** and planting programs.

Policy 7.4 Green Corridor Setback Standard: Require minimum 10-ft setbacks along key green corridors (bike/pedestrian paths) for planting continuous canopy cover and infiltration landscaping, with runoff performance standards.

Veloweg auf Kasernenstrasse verhindert Abbiegen in Zeughausstrasse

Wenn ich vom Stauffacher her auf dem Veloweg entlang der Kasernenstrasse fahre, wird durch die Bodenmarkierung effizient verhindert, dass ich legal in die Zeughausstrasse abbiegen kann, weil a) die Durchfahrt viel zu schmal ist und b) das Ganze nur ausgezeichnet ist für Velos, die von dort her auf den Veloweg fahren wollen :-/

Lässt sich da was anpassen? Oder ist etwas in Planung?

Bikeable app: Residents map barriers and suggest safer cycling routes. In implementing a similar tool city-wide, residents would request/monitor tree planting, suggest changes in parking permits, identify route safety issues.

Participatory design & Governance Bikeable, a Swiss-based platform, exemplifies participatory governance and urban design by enabling residents to directly map and report barriers to safe cycling. Through crowdsourced data, city planners gain real-time insights into infrastructure gaps, helping to prioritize investments in bike lanes, crossings, and safety measures. This model promotes co-production of urban mobility solutions, enhances transparency, and empowers communities to shape their own environments—key principles that can inform participatory planning initiatives in Southwood.

Western Creek Bend This segment anchors ecological & open space policies, demonstrating how floodplain zones can support both habitat continuity and community co-stewardship. Through Policy 1.1 and 1.4, parcels are rezoned for restoration with public access easements and flood-adapted vegetation, while Policy 1.3 fosters resident-led soil monitoring and land care.

Railroad Crossing A civic-ecological node where infrastructure and ecological systems intersect. Policies 4.1-4.4 guide civic retrofits, integrating bioswales, habitat corridors, and publicly accessible green edges. As a transit-adjacent site, it exemplifies how public buildings and mobility paths can function as resilience anchors.

Abandoned Railroad Spur This corridor illustrates mobility and ecological integration through Policies 7.1-7.4. Greenways and separated bike paths are designed with bioswales and participatory planting programs. This zone also demonstrates how linear infrastructure can become continuous habitat and stewardship corridors linking housing, food production, and ecological memory.

South 1st st Crossing At the edge of neighborhood residential zones, this area reflects Policies 2.1-2.4: ecological ADU retrofits, rainwater harvesting, and front yard greening programs. It also applies Policy 1.2 by linking resilience funding with infiltration performance. This interface zone enables gradual adaptive infill alongside ecological regeneration.

South Congress st Crossing Here, high-density housing and commercial use meet ecological voids. Through Policies 3.1-3.4 and 6.1-6.4, this zone supports rooftop gardens, compost systems, shared resource spaces, and zoning incentives for urban agroecology. Policy 6.1 further encourages bioremediation strategies to transform degraded soils into productive ecosystems.

Proposed Multispecies Land Use and Green Infrastructure System This map synthesizes the preceding analyses of infrastructural systems, shared urban functions, and natural-cultural ecologies into a consolidated land use vision for Southwood. It establishes the spatial foundation for a set of integrated planning goals and policy proposals developed in the next sections of this plan. Each land use category—ranging from neighborhood residential to civic, commercial, and ecological zones—is paired with four targeted policies. **Policies X.1** through **X.3** are designed to cultivate community-based land stewardship, emphasizing shared infrastructure, co-managed resources, and participatory knowledge systems. **Policies X.4**, by contrast, focus on adapting natural-cultural systems through expanded green infrastructure, regenerative land practices, and climate-resilient zoning standards. Together, these strategies promote a multifunctional urban landscape that aligns ecological performance with housing equity, mobility, and public life infrastructure.

Land Use map based on the City of Austin Land Use Inventory, 2025 (<https://data.austintexas.gov>).

IMPLEMENTATION TIMELINE

Former residential lots at Meadow Creek Circle, now restored as open space along Williamson Creek 100-year floodplain, Spring 2025

Governance & Funding

Zoning & Regulation

Engagement

Phase 1
Launch & Foundation

Phased Implementation

This three-phase implementation plan follows a process-based urban ecology framework that balances ecological restoration, community stewardship, and climate resilience.

The **Launch & Foundations** phase (2025-2027) establishes critical policies, zoning tools, and public programs. The **Build-Out & Integration** phase (2028-2035) focuses on scaling green infrastructure, activating civic and housing retrofits, and embedding ecological functions into the urban fabric. Finally, the **Consolidate & Expand** phase (2036-2040) ensures long-term performance tracking, land use transitions, and adaptive management.

Green Infrastructure Scaling

Civic Integration (Social & Civic Nodes)

Mobility & Green Corridors

Phase 2
Build Out & Integration

Monitoring & Metrics

Land Use Transition (Buyouts)

Adaptative Management

Phase 3
Consolidate & Expand

Focus Area	Key Actions
Governance & Funding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Launch Green Infrastructure Resilience Fund (Policy 1.2); • Create ADU Resilience Portal (2.1); • Initiate Green Corridor Setback Standard (7.4)
Zoning & Regulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enact "Void Space" Ordinance (1.4); • Rezone floodplain parcels (1.1)
Capacity & Knowledge Building	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish Soil & Forestry Knowledge Network (1.3); • Launch Soil Steward Mentorship (2.3); • Develop Fellowship program (4.3)
Pilot Projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Retrofit first civic building with green infrastructure (4.1); • Begin ADU pilot incentives in 2 overlay zones (2.2)
Engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Launch Community Mobility Labs (7.3); • Host workshops at Education Hubs (4.2)

Focus Area	Key Actions
Green Infrastructure Scaling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Add 3 micro-parks and 2+ miles of greenways (Goal 1) • Retrofit 50% of residential lots (Goal 2)
Housing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement Green ADU Overlay Zone across Southwood (2.2) • Require shared/co-op amenities in 60% of new builds (Goal 3)
Civic Integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Retrofit all civic buildings (4.1) • Activate eco-edges (4.4) • Ensure 10-min walk access to shared spaces (Goal 4)
High-Density Nodes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish 4 Community Nodes (Goal 5) • Apply Green Building + agroecological hub requirements (5.1, 5.2)
Circular Economy & Equity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Begin repurposing 25% of underutilized industrial parcels (6.1) • Enforce composting mandates (5.3, 6.3) • Expand cooperative zoning incentives (3.3, 6.3)
Mobility & Green Corridors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construct 4+ miles of green multimodal paths (Goal 7) • Implement bioswale/permeable paving standards (7.1, 7.2)

Focus Area	Key Actions
Monitoring & Metrics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement city-wide ecological performance tracking system (soil health, canopy, runoff, affordability)
Restoration & Productivity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Restore final 10+ acres of degraded soils (1.1) • Fully implement rooftop/tiny forest mandates (3.1, 6.1)
Equity & Climate Resilience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure 90% housing affordability target met (Goal 2) • Expand access to mobility nodes and green spaces
Land Use Transition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Repurpose 50% of underutilized commercial/industrial parcels (Goal 6)
Adaptive Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Refine zoning overlays and fund structures based on lessons learned • Update impervious cover and infiltration standards

APPENDIX

Collage visualizing Multifamily Residential areas in Southwood

Land Use	Policy Code	Southwood Plan Policy	CoA Existing Policy/Ordinance	Status - Improved through Southwood Plan
Ecological & Open Space	1.1	Rezone 5+ parcels in floodplain for ecological restoration with soil health targets and co-stewardship agreements	Watershed Protection Central Williamson Creek Vision Plan	Supported – Adds soil health targets and stewardship agreements for floodplain rezoning
	1.2	Create Green Infrastructure Resilience Fund expanding Urban Forest Fund to include soil restoration, compost, and infiltration goals	Urban Forest Replenishment Fund (Code § 6-3-5)	Partial – Expands fund purpose beyond trees to include soils, compost, and resilience
	1.3	Establish a hybrid Community Soil & Forestry Knowledge Network with digital tools	Imagine Austin and Sustainability Office support for green infrastructure	Partial – Operationalizes idea into a named, neighborhood-scale knowledge exchange network
	1.4	Set mandatory infiltration and restoration targets for soil and water quality in designated ecological cores and buffers.	Watershed Protection Ordinances (e.g., ECM)	Partial – Adds soil restoration and infiltration standards to watershed regulation.
Neighborhood Residential	2.1	One-stop ADU Resilience Incentive Portal combining green wretrofit grants for ADUs with priority for low-income households	Austin Water Rainwater Harvesting + Austin Energy Home Performance Program	Supported - Consolidates rebates, adds resilience framing and social equity targeting
	2.2	Green ADU Overlay Zones requiring ecological thresholds and incentives for native landscaping	Green Building standards available, not required for ADUs	Partial - Adds enforceable ecological thresholds and localized design overlay
	2.3	Soil Steward Mentorship Program linking residents with master gardeners and composters	Community gardening supported, no formal mentorship structure	New needed - Creates new resident education infrastructure with mentorship structure
	2.4	Designate overlays prioritizing rain gardens, rain tanks, and soil stewardship mentorship in residential lots adjacent to greenways.	Environmental Criteria Manual green BMPs, but voluntary	New needed – Creates enforceable overlays linked to stewardship programs and green retrofits.
Resilient Multi-family Housing	3.1	Green retrofit grants + rooftop garden mandates for buildings >6 units	Environmental Criteria Manual recommends green roofs/stormwater strategies	Partial - Turns recommendations into mandates and provides implementation funding
	3.2	Urban forestry partnerships to train residents in co-stewardship and composting systems	Urban Forestry Board and TreeFolks programming	Supported - Adds resident capacity-building and stewardship roles to existing programs
	3.2	Zoning bonuses for cooperatives that include shared kitchens, childcare, and green workspaces	No formal zoning incentive for coops; cooperative housing policies limited	Non-existing - Introduces a formal zoning incentive and program structure for climate coops
	3.4	Incentivize resident-managed eco-coops to manage rooftop gardens, compost hubs, and shared water harvesting systems	Green Building Program recommends green roofs (voluntary)	Partial – Adds community management model and mandatory incentive structure.

Land Use	Policy Code	Southwood Plan Policy	CoA Existing Policy/Ordinance	Status - Improved through Southwood Plan
Civic & Social Nodes	4.1	Retrofit 100% of civic buildings with bioswales, soil decompaction, or native understory planting	Green Building and Watershed Protection incentives (e.g., ECM Ch. 1)	Partial - Mandates ecological retrofits in all civic buildings; sets clear performance standard
	4.2	Co-locate green infrastructure education hubs within public schools and libraries	Nature in the City and school-based sustainability programs	Partial - Turns green learning into spatial policy tied to public buildings
	4.3	Create a Public Lands Stewardship Fellowship for training in soil care, urban agriculture, and environmental history	Volunteer programs exist, but no formalized civic ecology fellowship	New Needed - Creates structured, place-based stewardship program with training
	4.4	Allocate public parcels for micro-forests and "soil banks" to support native revegetation and stewardship training	Nature in the City and SFC programs (education-based)	New Needed – Institutionalizes microforest and soil restoration programs into civic land management.
Mixed Use & Community Nodes	5.1	Allow 5 stories via overlay if project includes green alley retrofits or permeable soil zones	Vertical Mixed Use zoning overlays allow height, not linked to GI	New Needed - Links density bonuses to green alley retrofits and soil permeability
	5.2	Provide grants for agroecological demonstration plots in plazas	Plaza programs exist (e.g., SFC), not tied to agroecology	Partial - Introduces agroecological learning into public plazas
	5.3	Require new commercial kitchens to separate organic waste and share data via a Soil Network Exchange	Commercial composting required only for large generators	Partial - Adds small-scale metrics and public reporting platform for organic waste
	5.4	Require 15% of public realm surfaces in nodes to be connected green-soil systems (canopy, permeable soils, rain gardens)	Tree planting incentives (limited, voluntary)	New Needed – Formalizes ecological continuity across blocks, not just isolated tree plantings.
Commercial & Repair-oriented Nodes	6.1	Fund on-site food forests or urban forests for bioremediation via the Soil & Forestry Fund	Pilot vertical gardens (e.g., downtown), no fund mechanism; Brownfields focus on safety, not biodiversity recovery	Partial - Adds soil/food systems to vertical retrofit funding scope; improve neighborhood-level resilience; introduces impervious % as a prioritization tool, Adds mandatory tiny forests and urban forestry for ecological bioremediation
	6.2	Create Green Industry Apprenticeship Network for composting, reuse, and repair trades	Workforce Development Division supports green careers	Partial - Proposes tailored, local apprenticeship for green/bio economy sectors
	6.3	Offer tax credits for soil decontamination and native planting on industrial parcels	Brownfield programs exist, limited soil/ecology focus	New Needed - Targets ecological soil repair with fiscal incentive structure
	6.4	Designate underutilized industrial parcels for soil decontamination projects tied to green economic reuse (e.g., food forests, reuse hubs)	Brownfield Redevelopment Programs (focused on safety)	Partial – Adds biodiversity restoration and productive reuse focus to soil clean-up strategies.

Land Use	Policy Code	Southwood Plan Policy	CoA Existing Policy/Ordinance	Status - Improved through Southwood Plan
Mobility Nodes	7.1	Implement Complete Streets with bioswales, permeable paving, and tree cover requirements	Street Design Guide and ECM support green elements	Supported - Strengthens Complete Streets with ecological performance metrics
	7.2	Fund green corridor plantings via the Urban Forest and Soil Health Fund	Urban Forest Fund exists; tree planting supported by Development Services	Partial - Expands scope of Urban Forest Fund to include green corridors
	7.3	Launch Community Mobility Labs for participatory street greening and biodiversity tracking	Placemaking and mobility innovation grants (e.g., ATX Walk/Bike/Places)	Partial - Institutionalizes public involvement in urban biodiversity and soil care
	7.4	Tie green corridor planting metrics (canopy, infiltration) to transportation funding eligibility and bonuses.	Urban Trails Master Plan – supports tree cover but non-binding	Partial – Links transportation and ecological corridor funding criteria explicitly.

Policy framework precedents

Policy 1.1 – Floodplain Restoration & Stewardship Zones

Precedent: Los Angeles River Revitalization Plan – Vacant lots along the river rezoned for habitat restoration and public trails.

Source: <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC96077>

Policy 2.1 – ADU Resilience Incentive Portal

Precedent: Portland’s Clean Energy Fund – Bundled retrofit funding for low-income households, including rainwater harvesting.

Source: <https://www.kitteryme.gov/home/news/new-adu-grant-program-available-kittery-homeowners>

Policy 3.4 – Resident-managed Eco-Coops

Precedent: Co-op City in the Bronx – Large cooperative integrating green roofs and community-run recycling/compost initiatives.

Source: <https://rocusa.org/why-resident-ownership/>

Policy 4.1 – Civic Building Retrofits with GI

Precedent: Seattle’s SEA Streets – Public infrastructure retrofitted with bioswales and permeable paving near schools and libraries.

Source: <https://www.architecturaldigest.com/story/one-americas-greenest-city-hall-buildings>

Policy 5.2 – Agroecological Demonstration Plots

Precedent: Prinzessinnengarten, Berlin – Public square transformed into urban farming plots with educational programs.

Source: <https://www.theguardian.com/environment/2024/nov/28/oosterwold-dutch-suburb-where-residents-must-grow-food-on-at-least-half-of-their-property>

Policy 6.4 – Soil Decontamination for Green Reuse

Precedent: The ReUse Center (Detroit) – Vacant brownfields remediated and activated for food forests and reuse-focused hubs.

Source: <https://nepis.epa.gov/Exe/ZyPURL.cgi?Dockey=P100AV48.TXT>

Policy 7.3 – Community Mobility Labs

Precedent: Better Block Projects (Dallas, TX) – Pop-up street redesigns that test ecological mobility solutions with community input.

Source: <https://sites.utexas.edu/uil/2022/12/19/community-hub-for-smart-mobility-chsm/>

Glossary

Term	Definition	Citation
Soil Health Metrics	Indicators of biological, physical, and chemical properties used to evaluate the resilience and function of soils in urban and peri-urban environments.	<i>de la Rosa D, et al. Mapping Urbanization as an Anthropogenetic Process. Land. 2023;12(5):1002.</i>
Tiny Urban Forest (Miyawaki Method)	Dense, multilayered forests planted with native species that restore biodiversity, sequester carbon, and improve infiltration in small urban lots.	<i>Miyawaki A. Restoration of living environment based on vegetation ecology: theory and practice. Ecol Res. 2004;19(1):83–90.</i>
Green Infrastructure	Nature-based systems—such as rain gardens, bioswales, and urban forests—designed to manage stormwater, reduce heat, and support biodiversity in urban settings.	<i>Benedict MA, McMahon ET. Green Infrastructure: Linking Landscapes and Communities. Island Press; 2006.</i>
Community Stewardship	A model of participatory governance where residents actively manage, restore, and co-create green spaces, infrastructure, and ecological functions.	<i>Tidball KG, Krasny ME. Civic ecology: a pathway for Earth Stewardship in cities. Front Ecol Environ. 2010;8(4):202–209.</i>
Eco-Cooperative Housing	Housing models that integrate ecological features (green roofs, shared gardens) with collective ownership and self-management of resources and amenities.	<i>Tummers L. The re-emergence of self-managed co-housing in Europe: A critical review of co-housing research. Urban Stud. 2016;53(10):2023–2040.</i>
Assemblage Urbanism	An approach that views urban spaces as dynamic constellations of human and non-human actors, systems, and ecologies in constant formation and transformation.	<i>McFarlane C. Assemblage and critical urbanism. City. 2011;15(2):204–224.</i>
Resilience Overlay Zoning	Regulatory tools that link climate adaptation performance (infiltration, canopy, permeability) to incentives or requirements within zoning overlays.	<i>Meerow S, Newell JP. Resilience and complexity: A bibliometric review and prospects for planning theory. J Plan Educ Res. 2019;39(3):283–297.</i>
Public Lands Fellowship	A programmatic tool for training local residents in ecological restoration, soil health, and stewardship of civic and green spaces.	<i>Kimmerer RW. Braiding Sweetgrass: Indigenous Wisdom, Scientific Knowledge and the Teachings of Plants. Milkweed Editions; 2013.</i>
Urban Agroecology	Application of agroecological principles—like biodiversity, local food systems, and organic practices—within urban or peri-urban settings to improve ecological and food resilience.	<i>Wezel A, Bellon S, Doré T, et al. Agroecology as a science, a movement and a practice. Sustain Agric. 2009;29(4):503–515.</i>

Postface: Toward a Living Neighborhood

*"I sowed the seeds that were ours –
and those that weren't.
I turned our minds into fields,
and cast a handful of seeds upon them" (1)*

Antônio Bispo dos Santos (1959–2023),
Brazilian Quilombola thinker and
agroecological philosopher

This plan closes where it began: with the recognition that land is not a blank canvas, but a living substrate—cultural, ecological, and historical. The Southwood Multispecies Land Use Plan has unfolded through layers of analysis, design, and visioning to propose a neighborhood shaped not solely by human utility, but by interdependence and regeneration. Yet, I acknowledge its limitations in both scope and reach. The current environmental crisis and climate emergency are superimposed upon long-standing social struggles. Nevertheless, my aim was to lay the groundwork for a new urban ecology: building from principles of climate resilience and biocultural stewardship, the plan reconfigures land not as commodity, but as commons—territory co-inhabited by diverse species, communities, and forms of knowledge.

Cities, like gardens, should be spaces of heterogeneity, porosity, and coexistence—as argued by Paola Viganò (1). In her words, a garden is “a place where bodies, lives, and dreams interact,” resisting totalizing logics in favor of open, evolving assemblages. The plan’s hybrid zones—where infrastructure meets habitat, where policy meets stewardship—echo Viganò’s call for projects that regenerate both soil and society.

This plan does not end with fixed outcomes, but with a posture that I aim for myself: one of care, connection to the landscape, and adaptive learning. It invites all stakeholders—planners, residents, and non-human species—into an evolving relationship with place, where floodplains become civic commons, rooftops become ecosystems, and governance is rooted in reciprocity. The urbanism proposed here is both physical and relational: new urban forms emerge from degraded soils, overlooked parcels, and cultural memories, taking form through the ongoing reweaving of needs, capacities, and possibilities.

In doing this work, my own neighborhood, Southwood, has become not just a site of planning, but a garden of possibility—like my own garden, shaped by its inhabitants rather than imposed upon them, always in transition. A moving garden, as Gilles Clément might say (2). The biopolitical stakes of this transformation are clear: to survive the climate crisis and systemic inequality, cities must re-ground themselves in life—not in abstraction, but in the concrete lives of people, plants, water, and soil.

I offer this plan not as a conclusion, but as a beginning: a framework, a vocabulary, and a shared imaginary from which Southwood—and perhaps other neighborhoods in Austin—can grow anew.

(1) Santos, Antônio Bispo dos. *A terra dá, a terra quer*. São Paulo: Edições Ubu, 2021.

(2) Viganò P. *Le jardin biopolitique: Pour une cité de la vie*. Genève: MétisPresses; 2023. 176 p..

(3) Clément G. *Le jardin en mouvement: de la Vallée au Jardin Planétaire*. Arles: Actes Sud; 2001.

This plan was developed in Spring 2025 as part of the course Sustainable Land Use Planning, taught by Prof. Katherine Lieberknecht at The University of Texas at Austin, School of Architecture, Community and Regional Planning Program. The work is the result of a semester-long research that explored regenerative land use strategies at the neighborhood scale, with a focus on ecological restoration, climate resilience, and environmental justice. Developed independently by Rodrigo D. Lima, the project integrates geospatial analysis, landscape infrastructure design, and policy frameworks to propose a multispecies land use vision for the Southwood neighborhood in Austin, Texas. It draws on planning theory, climate adaptation strategies, and ecological urbanism. The plan is informed by interdisciplinary scholarship and serves as a speculative yet actionable contribution to the future of just and resilient urban land systems.

All photographs and drawings were taken by the author or drawn by him.

Austin, Spring 2025

Author's garden in Southwood. Spring, 2024